

Productivity of Cassava- Based Farmers having Herders Conflicts in Ogbomoso Agricultural Zone, Oyo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Accelerated agricultural productivity is a vital pre-requisite for fast economic growth and development of a country, especially developing countries like Nigeria. However, crop sub-sector has been adversely affected by the conflicts stemmed up between crop farmers and herdsmen that further led to unrest in the local communities. This study therefore assessed the productivity of cassava- based farmers having herders conflicts in Ogbomoso Agricultural zone (ADP), Oyo State, Nigeria.

Multi-stage sampling technique was used to select 252 farmers in the study area due to the high incidence of herders' conflict with farmers. Primary data were collected with a structured questionnaire. Descriptive statistics was used to analyse the demographic characteristics of crop farmers and distribution of respondents by factors of production. Also, the productivity level of cassava-based farmers was determined by Total Factor Productivity (TFP) and its determinants were examined by exponential regression.

The results showed that majority of the respondents (88.5%) were male. Analysis of TFP showed that a mean productivity level of 5.21 was achieved by the cassava-based farmers. The exponential regression result revealed that household size ($p < 0.01$), adoption of soil conservation ($p < 0.01$), use of tractor ($p < 0.01$) as well as improved cassava stem cuttings ($p < 0.01$) had positive influence on the productivity level of cassava-based farmers while agricultural land use index ($p < 0.1$) had negative influence on their productivity.

This study therefore concluded that productivity levels among cassava-based farmers hinged on certain factors such as household size, soil conservation, tractor input, improved cassava varieties and agricultural land use index. The study recommends that the cassava crop productivity among farmers should be improved by the adoption of soil conservation, use of tractor, as well as improved cassava stem cuttings while ensuring large tract of agricultural land use index.

Keywords

Cassava- Based Farmers, Ogbomoso Agricultural Zone, Oyo State, Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

Cassava planting is domicile the smallholder arable crops due to its tolerant to bad weather and potential to suppress hunger among the masses (Onyemauwa, Nwafor, Aroh, and Ugbem-Onah, 2023). Given the various cassava programs and policies implemented over the years by government to raise farmers' efficiency and productivity in cassava production, it has become imperative to empirically analyze the relationship of total factor productivity and socioeconomic/demographic variables of cassava farmers in the face of herder attack. In essence, an assessment of the farmers-herders conflict and productivity of cassava-based farmers is necessary to establish the true facts about the extent of Fulani pastoralists' activities in our local areas which is obviously affecting crop productivity and people livelihoods all over the farming communities (Ndubuisi, 2018).

Nigeria have witnessed a series of violent communal clashes arising from the activities of the herders who move about on a daily basis with their cattle in search of water and green pastures just anyhow over cropland/rangeland belonged to other people (Sulaiman & Ja`afar-Furo, 2010). Consequently, many farmers and other villagers have lost their lives, experienced declining production in their crops and other livelihood activities. Given the importance of agriculture in the household livelihoods and the economy, it has become a necessity to address the challenges facing African farmers most importantly the conflict that leads to the loss of lives and properties (Mustapha, 2019). This study as a result, pointed out the following specific objectives and statistically estimated each of them in order to make policy recommendations on the prevailing matter between crop farmers and herders.

- i. Describe the socio-economic characteristics of cassava-based farmers in Ogbomoso Agricultural zone (ADP).
- ii. Describe th distribution of respondents by factors of production
- iii. Measure the productivity level of cassava -based farmers and its determinants in the study area

METHODOLOGY

The study was carried out in Ogbomoso Agricultural Development zone (ADP) of Oyo State, Nigeria. The estimated population of Ogbomoso Zone was 657,412 (NPC, 2006). Ogbomoso lies on 80 10' North latitude of the Equator and 40 10' East, of the Greenwich meridian (National Bureau of Statistis, 2020). The town lies within the derived savannah region and has a fairly high uniform temperature, moderate to heavy seasonal rainfall and high humidity. The mean annual temperature is 26.2⁰C. The highest degree of temperature is experience in March with a mean of 28.7⁰C while the lowest degree of temperature is experienced in August with a mean of 24.3⁰C. The mean annual rainfall is 1247mm. The state is endowed with a favourable climate and good vegetation for all year round cultivation of various cash and food crops, livestock rearing as well as processing activities on small scale. The place is mostly consist of the Yoruba ethnics being the Yoruba land, with so many Hausa, Igbo and Fulani herders inhabiting the bushes surrounding the cities. The population of this study however comprise all cassava-based farmers in Ogbomoso ADP zone.

Sampling Procedure and Data Collection

Multistage sampling technique was use for this research work. In the first stage, three Local Government Areas (LGAs) (Surulere, Ogo-oluwa and Oriire LGAs) from Ogbomoso zone were purposively selected because they are isolated rural areas where farmers-herders conflicts are common. The second stage involved the purposive selection of four wards in each LGA due to the high prevalence of crop farmers-herders' conflict in those areas, and this gives a total number of 12 wards. In the third stage, three communities were randomly selected from each of the 12 wards to make a total of 36 communities. Lastly, the list of registered cassava-based farmers was collected from the farm records provided in the ADP zone and a sample size of 252 crop farmers were selected based on probability proportionate scale introduced by Yamane (1967). According to Yamane sample size:

$$n = N/(1+N (e)^2) \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

N = assumed population size = 2500, and e = degree of desired precision (0.05).

$$n = 2500/(1+2500 (0.05)^2) =334 \text{ cassava-based farmers .}$$

At the end, a total of 252 sample size was used for this study because the rest of the questionnaires administered were not useful due to inconsistent information.

The data were collected through the use of structured questionnaire and interview schedule. The questionnaire was designed based on the objectives of this study. The main dataset collected for this research were socio-economics factors of crop farmers-herders, causes of conflicts, consequences of conflicts, conflict resolution methods and cassava farmers’ productivity and its determining variables such as land size, labour capital, fertilizers, water resource, cassava stem cuttings and others.

Data Analysis and Model Specification

Descriptive statistics like frequency, percentage and mean were used to describe socio-economic characteristics of crop farmers and distribution of respondents by factors of production. Also, the productivity level of cassava-based farmers was determined by Total Factor Productivity (TFP) index, exponential regression model was estimated to examine its determinants.

Measure the crop productivity level

Total Factor Productivity (TFP) is a method of calculating crop productivity by comparing an index of agricultural inputs to an index of outputs. This was used to compute the productivity level for each of the respondents. Crop production more often requires the combination of several inputs and measures need to reflect total factor productivity. TFP is implicitly given as:

$$TFP_i = \frac{Y}{\sum P_i X_i} \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

Where TFP_i = Total factor productivity for i th cassava farmer

Y = Quantity of cassava crop in (kg)

P = Unit price of i th variable input (₦)

X = Quantity of i th variable input

\sum = Summation

Exponential regression analysis

The exponential regression model was fitted to examine the determinants of productivity among cassava-based farmers as the lead functional form and specified as follows:

$$\ln TFP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \beta_5 X_5 + \beta_6 X_6 + \beta_7 X_7 + \mu \dots\dots\dots (4)$$

Where cassava crop productivity level is the dependent variable

X_i are independent variables such as X_1 = sex, X_2 = age of farmers, X_3 = household size, X_4 = agricultural land use index, X_5 = adoption of soil conservation X_6 = labour employed, X_7 =

improved stem cuttings, X_8 = use of tractor, and X_9 = farm size. Also, β_0 and μ are constant and random error terms respectively.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Socio-economic Characteristics of Respondents

Distribution of respondents based on their socio-economic characteristics is presented in Table 1. The characteristics of the respondents considered include: the sex of the respondents, their ages, marital status, household size, educational status, religion and so on. From the table, it was revealed that 88.50% of the respondents were male, while 11.50% of the respondents were female. This implies that majority of the respondents were male. Majority 91.70% of the respondents were married, with only 6.30% who are single. Marriage saddles people with one kind of responsibility or the other, also there is availability increasing household size. It was also reported from the finding of the study that 35.30% of the respondents were Christians, 61.50% of the respondents were Muslims, and 3.20% of the respondents were Traditionalist, this explained that the role of religion can be described as just a side track or passes by when studying another phenomenon.

Furthermore, all the sample respondents had one form of education or the other, education helps people in adoption and adaptation of new technologies and innovations. It was revealed that, 7.10% of the respondents were Hausa, 36.10% of the respondents were Fulani and 56.70% of the respondents were Yoruba with mean age of 53 years which implies that the respondents are still in their active age hence the production is expected to be improved and there is tendency of settling the conflict between farmers and herders in the area.

In addition, majority 46.43% of the respondents had spent between 11 and 20 year in the area, while only 0.4% of them had been residing in the area between 61 and 70 years with mean year of residence of 30years. Also, 63.50% of the respondents are farmers, 18.70% of the respondent's occupation were cattle rearing while 17.90% of the respondents' occupation were farming and cattle rearing. Farming is predominant occupation among the people in the area i.e. the households had chosen farming as a means of livelihood hence there was improve in food productivity. More than half 68.26% had between 6 and 10 household size, while only 3.57% had between 11 and 15 members with mean household size of 6 persons. The respondent's large household size will therefore provide family labour.

Table 1: Distribution of Respondents based on Socio-economic characteristics

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Cumulative Frequency	
Gender				
Male	223	88.50	88.50	
Female	29	11.50	100.00	
Marital Status				
Married	231	91.70	91.70	
Single	16	6.30	98.00	
Divorced	3	1.20	99.20	
Widow	2	0.80	100.00	
Religion				
Christianity	89	35.30	35.30	
Muslim	155	61.50	96.80	
Traditional	8	3.20	100.00	
Educational Level				
Quranic	43	17.10	17.10	
Adult	25	9.90	27.00	
Nomadic	15	6.00	32.90	
Primary	63	25.00	57.90	
Secondary	32	12.70	70.60	
Tertiary	11	4.40	75.00	
No Formal	63	25.00	100.00	
Ethnic group				
Hausa	18	7.10	7.10	
Fulani	91	36.10	43.30	
Yoruba	143	56.70	100.00	
Age (Years)				
21 – 40	49	19.45	19.45	
41 – 60	134	53.17	72.62	
61 and above	69	27.38	100.00	Mean = 53.20
Years of Residence				
1 – 20	117	46.43	46.43	
21 – 40	50	19.84	66.27	
41 – 60	84	33.33	99.60	
61 – 70	1	0.40	100.00	
Occupation				
Farming	160	63.50	63.50	
Cattle Rearing	47	18.70	82.10	
Farming and Cattle Rearing	45	17.90	100.00	
Household Size				
1 – 5	71	28.17	28.17	Mean = 6.36
6 – 10	172	68.26	96.43	
11 – 15	9	3.57	100.00	
Total	252	100.00		

Source: Field Survey analysis, 202

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Distribution of Respondents by factors of production

Table 2 revealed that, 58.73% of the respondents acquired their land through owned, 28.57% of the respondents acquired their land through lease or rented, 9.50% of the respondents acquired their land through friend and 3.20% of the respondents does not have access to land. The result revealed that a high percentage of the respondents acquired land by buying which means the lands they use have been cultivated for a long time which is left with less fertility. About 73.41% of the respondents owned 1-5 ha of farmland, 23.81% of the respondents cultivated 6-10 ha of farm land and 2.80% of the respondents owned 11 – 15 ha of farm land. This revealed that a high significant percentage had a large area of lands to cultivate for farming. About (93.65%) of the respondent bought the farmland between $\leq 100,000$, 0.79% of the respondent bought their farm land between ₦ 101,000 – 150,000, 1.19% of the respondent bought their farm land between ₦151,000 – 200,000, 1.19% of the respondent bought their farm land between ₦ 201,000 – 250,000, 1.59% of the respondent bought their farm land between ₦251,000 – 300,000 while 1.59% of the respondent bought their farm land between ₦ 301,000 – 350,000. The mean cost of land is ₦ 26102.10. The table also revealed that, 13.89% of the respondents uses skilled as their source of labour for farming activities, 53.57% of the respondents uses unskilled as their source of labour for farming activities, 8.33% of the respondents uses both unskilled and semi-skilled as their source of labour for farming activities, 11.90% of the respondents uses both Skilled and unskilled as their source of labour for farming activities, 7.14% of the respondents uses both family and hired labour as their source of labour for farming activities while 5.17% of the respondents uses hired labour as their source of labour for farming activities.

Table 2: Distribution of Respondents by Factors of Production

Factors of production	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Cumulative Frequency
Mode of land acquisition			
Own land	148	58.73	58.73
Lease or rent	72	28.57	87.30
Access through friend	24	9.50	96.80
No access to land	8	3.20	100.00
Farm size (ha) under cultivation			
1 – 5	185	73.41	73.41
6 – 10	60	23.81	97.20
11 – 15	7	2.80	100.00 Mean: 4.8ha
Cost of land			
≤ 100,000	236	93.65	93.65
101,000 – 150,000	2	0.79	94.44
151,000 – 200,000	3	1.19	95.63
201,000 – 250,000	3	1.19	96.82
251,000 – 300,000	4	1.59	98.41
301,000 – 350,000	4	1.59	100.00 Mean: 26102.10
Source of labour			
Skilled	35	13.89	13.89
Unskilled	135	53.57	67.46
Unskilled and Semi-Skilled	21	8.33	75.79
Skilled and Unskilled	30	11.90	87.69
Family and Hired Labour	18	7.14	94.83
Hired Labour	13	5.17	100.00
Total	252	100.00	

Source: Field Survey analysis, 2024

Farm productivity level of cassava-based farmers

The result of the analysis of the productivity levels of the farmers measured in quantity of cassava produced per naira cost of all variable inputs used is summarized in Table 3. Majority (38.61%) of the respondents had productivity levels of between 4.1 and 6.0 while about 30.30% had productivity levels of between 6.1 and 8.0. However, about 16.35% of them had productivity levels between 2.1 and 4.0 also, 8.35% farmers had a range productivity levels between 0 and 2.0 while the least (6.39%) of them attained a productivity levels of 8.0 and above. Analysis shows that a mean productivity level of 5.21 was achieved by the cassava-based farmers. Generally, the result shows that the farmers were productive in their cassava farming activities. This is shown by the productivity level of the farmers, which is greater than 1. This implies that the cassava-based farmers got higher returns from their investments in cassava farming.

Table 3: Distribution of farm productivity levels among the respondents

Farm productivity level	Frequency	Percentage
0 – 2.0	22	8.35
2.1 – 4.0	40	16.35
4.1 – 6.0	97	38.61
6.1 – 8.0	77	30.30
> 8.0	16	6.39
Total	252	100.00

Mean of productivity 5.21

Source: Field Survey analysis, 2024

Determinants of Productivity of Cassava-based Farmers using Exponential Regression Model

The exponential regression analysis was fitted to examine the determinants of farm productivity among cassava-based farmers. The model has a goodness of fit as indicated by F-value, R-square metrics, number of significant predictors in the Table 4. The F-value (Prob>F=0.000) is significant at 1% level indicating the joint significant effect of all explanatory variables that entered into model while the R-square value of 16.59% obtained also explains the sources of variations in the dependent (farm productivity).

According to this result, five explanatory variables which are household size, land access, adoption of soil conservation measures, use of tractor, and fertilizers were statistically significant. It was found that household size has positive relationship with productivity level among cassava-based farmers and significant at 1% level. This result indicates that a unit increase in the household size within cassava farmers would lead to a corresponding increase in the farm productivity level. It therefore, evident that the family labour contributed more energy and resources to cassava production in the study area. The family farm is a common feature that cuts across various agricultural structures and plays a critical role in food production systems (Graeb *et al.*, 2016). Family farms are the main form of agricultural organization worldwide, accounting for almost 80% of global food production, and 98% of food production in Sub-Saharan Africa.

Agricultural land use index was significant at 10% level and exhibits an inverse relationship with the farm productivity among cassava-based croppers. This implies that an additional unit change in agricultural land use index with times causes reduction in farm productivity, if the problems associated to land use for agricultural purpose practices are not solved. It is evident that agricultural land use is steadily declining in value and presently facing serious challenges of population pressure, encroachment, conflict, dispute and degradation. This suggests that the land reform and land use decree be reviewed in order to sustain agricultural practices in Nigeria.

The adoption of soil conservation measures was found to be significantly determined the farm productivity level among cassava-based farmers. The finding shows that soil conservation is positively related to the farm productivity and significant at 1% level, it implies that as the farmers adopt more conservation measures their farm productivity level also increases. This suggests adequate and appropriate application of the recommended soil conservation techniques by the farmers so as to maintain soil fertility and enhance productivity level. The result corroborate with the a priori expectation. The better the land quality, the higher the production level (Dayanandan and Ataro, 2018).

The use of tractor for farm operations such as land clearing, is very crucial to ease or simplify the farm works and facilitate improvement in arable production. The coefficient of the farm tractorization shows a direct relationship with the agricultural productivity and significant at 1% level. It signifies that an increase level of farm mechanization can lead to increase production

and farm productivity *ceteris paribus*. This finding therefore suggests that the farm owners should try possible means to shift towards farm tractorization especially the medium and large scale farmers, in order to enhance agricultural productivity growth.

Lastly, planting of improved stem cuttings was positively significant at 1% level and it indicates an increasing contribution to productivity level of cassava-based farmers. This result suggests that the farmers need to cultivate more of the improved varieties of cassava in order to boost cassava production in the study area. Coupled with this, hired labour use and farm size were other variables specified in the model but they are not significant at any level. However, the farm size has positive coefficient which indicated that more farm land is associated with increase cassava production. This finding is inconsistent with the result of Onyemauwa, *et al.*, (2023).

Table 4: Exponential Functional Analysis of Determinants of Cassava-based Productivity Level

Independent variables	Coefficients	Standard errors	t- value	P >t
Constant term	0.9422334	0.2515715	3.75	0.000
Sex	-0.0246098	0.0939872	-0.26	0.794
Age of farmers	0.0011898	0.0026162	0.45	0.650
Household size	0.0396125	0.0138364	2.86***	0.005
Agric. land use index	-0.258919	0.1350032	-1.92*	0.056
Soil conservation	0.3923825	0.1145561	3.43***	0.001
Hired labour use	-0.002195	0.0073312	-0.30	0.765
Use tractor	0.1851503	0.059492	3.11***	0.002
Improved stem cutting	0.2005836	0.0614779	3.26***	0.001
Farm size	0.0661197	0.0555601	1.19	0.276

Number of obs = 252, Prob > F = 0.0000, R-square = 0.1659

Source: Field Survey analysis, 2024

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study concluded the productivity levels among cassava-based farmers hinged on certain factors such as household size, soil conservation, tractor input, improved cassava varieties and agricultural land use index. Based on the findings of this study, the study recommends that high productivity levels should be encouraged among cassava-based farmers through the adoption of soil conservation measures, use of tractor as well as improved varieties of cassava stem cuttings in order to increase production in the study area.

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